

Milestone: MS15 - Key selected interoperability challenge demonstrations implemented

Lead Participant: University of Oslo

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Due: 30.11.2024

Date of Completion: 24.09.2024

Means of Verification

- [Slides](#) presented to all partners during the EOSC-ENTRUST first evaluation and adoption workshop with accompanying [collaborative meeting minutes](#)
- [Milestone Report M15](#)
- Section 5.2.1 and Figure 5.2.3 in [EOSC-ENTRUST D13.4 - Year one version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework](#)
- [Code in GitHub](#)
- <https://pypi.org/project/tsd-api-client/3.5.3/>

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

No delays.

The milestone was successfully completed ahead of schedule and presented on workshop in Helsinki on September 24-25.

Project participants & others

Milestone contributors include six individuals from the University of Oslo and the University of Bergen.

Event Attendees/Audience: The presentation was part of a workshop organized by Architecture WP13, held in Helsinki. Participants from all project WPs attended in person, totaling 40 attendees, along with several remote participants.

Next action steps

Outcomes from M15 will feed into:

- [D13.4](#) Year one version of EOSC-ENTRUST blueprint and interoperability framework
- [D13.2](#) - Training package for EOSC-ENTRUST Year one: Blueprint and Interoperability framework